

ADSORPTION OF ALCOHOL ON SILICA GEL

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The effects of ageing and different temperatures of evacuation on silica gel have been studied in respect of adsorption of anhydrous alcohol. There was little change in adsorption isotherms as long as the temperature of evacuation did not exceed a certain limit. Beyond this the adsorption improved at all pressures for the samples of gel used. Ageing improved adsorption at higher pressures but depressed it at lower ones. A fresh gel did not show hysteresis unless the temperature of evacuation was about 300°. Older gels or those evacuated at higher temperatures showed permanent hysteresis in adsorption, but the hysteresis region was not alike for different samples of the gel. About 2% of the adsorbed liquid could not be pumped out even at elevated temperatures. The gel had sometimes to be flushed a number of times to obtain reproducible adsorption branches.

In a previous communication (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1945, 49, 226) the author has studied the adsorption of methyl, ethyl, *n*-propyl and *n*-butyl alcohol on silica gel. The adsorption isotherms plotted as the amount adsorbed per g. of the gel, (x/m) against the pressures of the vapours, were found to possess a feature which did not appear with some other vapours such as hydrocarbons, esters and ketones (*Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci. India*, 1944, 14, 85). These isotherms of alcohols appeared to consist of several loops whereas in other cases they were more or less smooth. It was therefore decided to study the adsorption of at least ethyl alcohol in fuller detail, working with a fresh sample of silica gel and with the alcohol purified and dehydrated with greater care than before.

EXPERIMENTAL

A sample of silica gel was prepared in large quantity. Commercial sodium silicate syrup was thinned down with water and diluted to a density of 1.12. Commercial hydrochloric acid was diluted to a density of 1.05. Equal quantities of the two solutions, 30-35 c.c. each, were then mixed with vigorous shaking in a large boiling tube. The clear solution, slightly yellowish due to the presence of iron, was collected in shallow porcelain basins and allowed to gelate at room temperature. After three or four days, when it had set to a stiff gel, it was cut into small pieces, washed with distilled water to remove most of the electrolytes, and then heated on a water-bath with intermittent changes of water for another 2 or 3 days. This operation eliminated all the remaining impurities in the gel while at the same time permitting it to age at about 70°-80°. The gel, a little shrunken in size, was now in the form of perfectly transparent, colorless lumps. It was desiccated in a porcelain basin over the water-bath. The lumps were now greatly reduced

in size and the material became hard and brittle. It was then transferred to a muffle furnace and kept at 350°-400° for 3 hours. On cooling, it was stored in a bottle over phosphorus pentoxide. This sample of the gel is described as the "UCL gel".

Another sample of the gel on which the earlier measurements had been carried out (Gyani, Thesis, Patna University, 1944, p. 99 *et seq*) was also used for comparison. It had been prepared in the same way as described above except that the gelation had taken place at a higher temperature, and the final desiccation was done on a sand-bath at 300°-350° in a current of dry air. This sample is called the "Patna gel".

The commercial absolute alcohol was kept in contact with some highly desiccated silica gel to remove any strongly adsorbable impurities. It was then stored overnight over freshly ignited quicklime. The final dehydration was done over aluminium-mercury couple after which the liquid was fractionated (b.p. 78.5° at 767.15 mm., s.p. gr., 0.791 at 18°, vapour pressure at 35°, 101 mm).

The adsorption apparatus used was similar to those described previously (*loc. cit.*). The amount of adsorption at a given pressure was determined by observing the increase in the weight of a bulb containing a known amount of the adsorbent. A liquid trap, cooled in solid carbon dioxide, effectively prevented any vapour from entering the pump in the new apparatus. As before, the experiments were carried out at 35° by enclosing the entire apparatus in a thermostat. The pressures were read on a metre scale rigidly attached to the mercury manometer with the help of a telescope placed 4' away. The error due to changes of level in the reservoir of mercury was small, about 0.5 mm. for 100 mm. change in pressure. The fractional error being constant had simply the effect of shortening the unit itself by about 0.5% and was consequently neglected. One can see that in the present method every single observation is absolute and not affected by accumulated errors from previous measurements to which the volumetric methods are open. It is significant that in these measurements reproducibility is good, even in the region of saturation where Coolidge (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 46, 603) found unsatisfactory results. Further, experiments in adsorption and desorption are carried out with equal ease and accuracy.

In the earlier measurements at Patna (Thesis, Patna University, *loc. cit.*) the gel had been freshly prepared and was evacuated at about 250°. The heating was done by a Bunsen flame, the bulb having been wrapped in a few folds of asbestos paper. The adsorption and desorption isotherms were found to coincide in these measurements with this gel, that is to say, no hysteresis was detected. When the experiment was repeated in London with the fresh UCL gel, evacuated at a higher temperature a large hysteresis appeared prior to saturation. The temperature of activation, the mode and duration of heating

and the age of the gel might each be playing a part in the appearance of hysteresis. It was therefore decided to take measurements with both the UCL gel and the Patna gel, which was now about two years old, after a final evacuation at different temperatures. The UCL gel was heated in different experiments both by a Bunsen flame and by enclosing it in an electrically heated oven whereby a more uniform temperature could be attained. Some of the results of these measurements are shown diagrammatically in the accompanying figures. The amounts of adsorption, x/m , are expressed in g. mol. of the liquid per g. of gel $\times 10^{-4}$. The pressures are in mm. of mercury. The different treatments of the gel prior to adsorption measurements are denoted by capital letters. These treatments are recorded in Table I.

The results of adsorption measurements with the UCL gels A, B, C, each of which had been heated in a flame during evacuation are shown in Fig. 1. The isotherm for the gel UCL-B has been shifted along the adsorption axis by 10×10^{-4} mol. per g. from that for the gel A for the sake of clarity. The isotherm for C has been similarly shifted with respect to that for B. The adsorption is quite large even for the smallest pressures recorded.

FIG. 1

For the gel UCL-A and -B the adsorption curve denoted by crosses and dotted lines lies considerably below the desorption curve denoted by circles and full lines. The difference is less for the gel B which was heated for the second time, and vanishes with the gel C which was heated for the third time. It is likely that this difference between the adsorption and desorption isotherms was due to imperfect flushing of the gel. The difference between the adsorption and desorption isotherms in the pressure range of 55-75 mm. was large and

remained as such during successive heatings of the gel. In other words, a permanent hysteresis region existed at these pressures. It can be observed that the shapes and locations of the isotherms are substantially retained during the successive heatings at the same temperature.

Some of the results of measurements on the cold, evacuated UCL gel D and the gels E and F, evacuated under uniform electrical heating, are shown graphically in Fig. 2. The first few measurements with D were very erratic on the adsorption side but the adsorption curve gradually settled down in the close neighbourhood of the first desorption curve after many flushings of the gel with vapour. The adsorption and desorption points occurred close together for the gels E and F and could be represented by the same curves in the case of each gel. As a matter of fact, the three isotherms almost overlap each other so that to obtain clarity the isotherm for E has been shifted 10×10^{-4} mol. per g. downwards along the x/m axis. There is no evidence for any permanent hysteresis for the gels D and E, but a small one could be detected for the gel F in the pressure region 52-67 mm.

FIG. 2

The isotherms obtained with the gels Patna G, cold evacuated, and Patna H, evacuated at 320° under uniform electrical heating, are shown in Fig. 3. These graphs are similar to those for the gels UCL-A, B or C. Hysteresis occurs with each gel and extends over a large pressure range, viz. 50-80 mm. Both the adsorption and desorption isotherms in this region are steeper than the corresponding ones for the UCL gels.

The isotherms described above obviously belong to three distinct groups. The first consists of the gels UCL-A, B and C. The second comprises the gels UCL-D, E and F and the third, the Patna gels, G and H. For the sake of comparison representative isotherms of each group are reproduced in Fig. 4. The isotherms of three additional gels, Patna I and II and Patna J, whose

FIG. 3

adsorptions had been determined at an earlier date at Patna, are also included in this diagram. It is found that all the Patna gels form a bunch by

FIG. 4

themselves towards the lower pressures and so do the UCL gels. The latter show about 10% better adsorption in this region.

Effect of Temperature of Evacuation

One can see from Fig. 4 that the maximum amount of adsorption, *i.e.* the adsorption attained at the highest pressures, may differ greatly for different samples of the gel. The values of maximum adsorption are conveniently summarised in Table I.

TABLE I

Description of the gel.	Age.	Mode of heating.	Temperature of evacuation.	Max. adsorption (g. mol. per g. gel $\times 10^4$).
Patna J.	2 years	Flame	Over 450°	101
Patna H	3 ..	Electrical	320°	88-91
Patna G	3 ..	No heating	30°	83-84
UCL-A, B	1 month	Flame	Over 450°	88
UCL-C	2	Over 450°	84
UCL-D	3 ..	No heating	30°	70
UCL-E, F	3 ..	Electrical	200, 300°	69
Patna I	Some ..	Flame	About 300°	70
Patna II	Some	About 400°	79

The effect of temperature of evacuation on adsorption can be clearly observed by comparing the maximum amounts of adsorption attained by gels of comparable ages. Among the Patna gels the best adsorption is shown by the gel J which was evacuated at the highest temperature. The value of maximum adsorption for the cold evacuated gel Patna G increased from 83-84 units to 88-91 when the temperature of evacuation was increased to 320°. Although the gels UCL-D, E, F were evacuated at quite different temperatures, the saturation values remained practically constant at 69-70 units. But when the temperature of evacuation was raised to over 450°, *e.g.*, in the case of the gel UCL-A, the value came up to 88, an increase of over 25%.

A curious isotherm was given by the gel Patna II. Up to a pressure of 60 mm. the graph coincided entirely with the Patna I isotherm. The two were satisfactorily reversible in this region and there was no evidence of hysteresis. When the gel Patna I was heated to a higher temperature to obtain the gel Patna II, a new portion of the adsorption isotherm appeared near the saturation pressure. By an oversight the desorption curve between 80 and 60 mm. was not mapped, but by comparison with the gel UCL-A, which gives a similar graph, it is probable that hysteresis existed and the author's earlier statement (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1945, 49, 226) requires correction. In this connection it is interesting to note that the upper part of the alcohol isotherm on the gel Patna G was again missed in the first few adsorption measurements. The graph came to an end along the dotted line marked 1 in Fig. 3. After several flushings of the gel with vapour the adsorption isotherm rose up as

shown by the dotted line marked 2 and remained constant there. The anomalous behaviour noted in these experiments recalls some earlier observations such as those of McBain ("The Sorption of Gases and Vapours by Solids", p. 94, G. Routledge and Sons, Ltd, London, 1932).

Recalling the observations already recorded, it is easy to see that the temperature of evacuation plays an important part in determining the occurrence of hysteresis. Thus, among the fresh UCL gels, permanent hysteresis was not observed as long as the temperature of evacuation was below 300° (the gels D and E). At 320° the hysteresis appeared but was quite small in size (the gel F). When the temperature of evacuation was increased to about 450°, the region of hysteresis became large. A similar effect probably took place with the gels Patna I and II as just described.

The observations show that the hysteresis in the adsorption of alcohol by fresh samples of silica gel appears only when the gel has been evacuated well over 300°. This factor might explain the absence of hysteresis from the isotherms of water on silica gel obtained by Patrick, Davis, and Barclay ("Colloid Symposium Annual", 7, p. 130, Johns Hopkins, 1929). Patrick evacuated his gel at 350°. Probably a higher temperature of evacuation for his particular gel might have brought out hysteresis.

Effect of Ageing

It is observed from these experiments that the age of the gels plays an important part in determining the amount of adsorption and its variation with pressure. The effect of increasing age is often similar to that of increasing temperature of evacuation. For instance, both of them produce a rounding off of the isotherm towards higher pressures so that it merges gradually into the saturation portion (cf. Patna I and Patna J, or UCL-D and UCL-A, Fig. 4).

Increase in age probably depresses the amount of adsorption in the region of lower pressures (cf. Patna J and Patna H, Fig. 4), but definitely increases it in the region of higher pressures. This fact is clearly brought out by comparing values of maximum adsorption for the gels UCL-D, E, and F, which, in spite of evacuation at different temperatures remains constant at 69-70 g. mol. $\times 10^{-4}$ per g. of the gel. If a similar rule held for the gels Patna I and G we have to conclude that the increase in the value of the maximum adsorption from 70 to 84 units is due to the ageing of the gel. Manegold (*Kolloid Z.*, 1939, 81, 19) quotes that three samples of silica gel due to van Bemmelen had pore volumes 0.410, 0.485, and 0.570 when fresh, six months old and five years old respectively. The figures correspond with an increase in adsorption of over 15% in six months and over 35% in five years, whereas the Patna gel under discussion shows a total increase of about 20% in 3 years. Holmes and Elder (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1931, 35, 82) have observed a decrease in pore volume in contrast to these results with increasing age for eleven samples of silica gel.

The present observations also tend to show that the temperature of evacuation is not the only factor which determines hysteresis. A large hysteresis region occurs with the gel Patna G which was evacuated only at room temperature. So, the occurrence of hysteresis in this case must be ascribed to the ageing alone. The shapes of the hysteresis region for the aged Patna gels and the fresh UCL gels differ and so do their sizes. It appears that these differences are again due to ageing, noting the fact that if hysteresis did exist with the gel Patna II, its shape must have been similar to that for the gel UCL-A.

Changes in the Gel Structure

It is generally considered at present that the internal structure of silica gel consists of a conglomeration of small particles or micelles of the gel material partly coalescing with each other and partly separated by empty capillary spaces which may normally contain air and water. These capillary spaces may be anything in dimensions between sub-microscopic and molecular. The same is true about the micelles. The fact that a piece of raw silica gel shrinks greatly in size on progressive drying though retaining its transparency shows that these dimensions must undergo changes according to circumstances. Gels with such structures are potentially capable of both surface adsorption and capillary condensation.

Sigmoid adsorption isotherms, such as the ones obtained in these experiments, are usually considered to involve mainly surface adsorption at lower pressures and mainly capillary condensation at higher pressures. The Brunauer-Emmett-Teller theory (Brunauer, "Adsorption of Gases and Vapours", p 140, Oxford University Press, 1944) seeks to unify these two processes in a single expression for the amount of adsorption. These workers consider that the lower parabolic part of such isotherms ("point B") marks the completion of a unimolecular layer of adsorbed molecules so that if the amount of adsorption corresponding to this point is determined one can have a measure of the internal area of the adsorbent.

The observations recorded above, as far as they go, tend towards the the following conclusions :

(1) Evacuating above certain temperatures (depending upon different gels) improves adsorption at all pressures (cf. Table I and the isotherms of UCL-D and A or Patna G, H, and J).

(2) Ageing improves adsorption at higher pressures but depresses it at lower pressures (cf. isotherms of Patna I and Patna H).

(3) Evacuation above a certain temperature may produce hysteresis (cf. isotherms of UCL-D, E and A, B, C, F or Patna I and II).

(4) Ageing beyond a certain limit appears to produce a similar effect (cf. isotherms of Patna I and G, H).

It appears to the author that these observations may be explained if one considers that evacuating above certain temperatures brings about shrinkage of individual micelles. The shrinkage would be accompanied by a general diminution in the area of individual micelles, but if the shrinkage is considerable, as it should be if temperatures are high, the areas of contact between the micelles may open up, thus increasing the total surface. Continued heating at low temperatures may not only shrink the micelles but probably smooths out the roughness on the surface by a process of sintering of the protuberances. Ageing may produce similar effects. Hence, under these conditions there would be a small diminution of adsorption corresponding to "point B" as is observed in these experiments. Conditions bringing about shrinkage and sintering will naturally increase the capillary volume of the adsorbent, so that elevated temperatures of evacuation or ageing should produce an increase in the capillary adsorption, as has been noted above.

It further appears to the author that a certain minimum width of capillaries is necessary before hysteresis may appear. To produce wide capillaries prolonged ageing or evacuation at elevated temperatures would be necessary which appears to explain in a simple way the last two observations recorded above.

Another important observation from these experiments was that about 2% of the adsorbed alcohol was irreversibly retained by the gel and it could not be pumped out into the best vacuum available at the highest temperatures employed in these experiments. The gel became distinctly coloured after a prolonged series of runs-although no products of the decomposition of alcohol could be detected by ordinary analytical methods. This irreversible retention of the adsorbed liquid agrees with many previous observations (McBain, "Sorption", p. 94 ; Brunauer, *loc cit.*, p. 419). It appears that a portion of the alcohol is adsorbed on active points in the gel structure as considered in a previous paper by the author (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1945. 49, 442).

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